

Synthesis of Coumarins and Chromones from 4-Chloro- and 4-Bromo-1-naphthol.

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Clayton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 2018) observed that in condensations of phenols with β -ketonic esters the presence of a halogen atom in the phenolic nucleus greatly hinders Pechmann's reaction forming coumarins and it was found by Chakravarti (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 25,31) that the introduction of a negative substituent like Cl or NO_2 in monohydric phenols favours Simonis' reaction forming chromones. Chakravarti and Ghosh (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 622) found, however, that negative substituents like Cl or NO_2 in the molecule of resorcin, which has the faculty of the formation of coumarins with great readiness, are not prejudicial to the formation of coumarins: chlororesorcin condenses with acetoacetic esters, irrespective of the complexity of the α -alkyl substituent, forming coumarins either in presence of sulphuric acid (Pechmann's reaction) or phosphorus pentoxide (Simonis' reaction).

In view of the fact that α -naphthol shows much reactivity in the formation of coumarins such that even by changing the condensing agent for phosphorus pentoxide it condenses with β -ketonic esters yielding coumarins and not chromones (Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 407) the condensations of the halogenated α -naphthols with acetoacetic esters have been studied in order to see whether there is any hindrance to the coumarin formation and the chromone formation is facilitated due to the presence of the halogen atom.

4-Chloro-1-naphthol, prepared by a modification of the method of Kast (*Ber.*, 1911, 44, 1337. *vide* experimental) by the action of sulphuryl chloride on a hot chloroform solution of α -naphthol, condenses with acetoacetic ester and α -chloro-acetoacetic ester to form 6-chloro-4-methyl-1:2- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone* (I, R = H; R' = Me) and 3:6-dichloro-4-methyl-1:2- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone respectively in a yield of 90% and identical coumarins are also obtained using phosphorus pentoxide as the condensing agent.

* The naphthapyrones, described in this paper, have been named according to the nomenclature proposed by Dey and Lakshminarayana, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 153.

It is, however, remarkable that with the introduction of an alkyl substituent in the acetoacetic ester molecule as in the case of methyl-, ethyl-, propyl-, isobutylacetoacetic esters 4-chloro-1-naphthol gives in the presence of sulphuric acid a coumarin (I, R = Me, Et, Pr, C₄H₉; R' = Me), but using phosphorus pentoxide the corresponding chromone (II, R = Me; R' = Me, Et, Pr, C₄H₉) is obtained, not a trace of coumarin being formed. All these chromones contain a reactive methyl group in the 2-position, hence they are easily characterised by the formation of crystalline styryl derivatives (II, R = CH:CH-C₆H₅; R' = Me, Et, Pr, C₄H₉) when condensed with benzaldehyde in presence of alcoholic sodium ethoxide, while the corresponding isomeric 4-methylcoumarins are unchanged by this treatment (*cf.* Heilbron, Barnes and Morton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2569 and Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 129).

(I)

(II)

4-Chloro-1-naphthol has also been condensed with benzyl-acetoacetic ester, α -phenyl-acetoacetic ester, benzoyl acetic ester, aceto-succinic ester and acetone dicarboxylic acid to give coumarins. The condensations of 4-chloro-1-naphthol with acetoacetic ester and methyl-acetoacetic ester have been studied with different condensing agents, e.g. sodium acetate, sodium ethoxide, phosphoric acid, etc., and it has been found that, if condensation takes place at all, coumarins are always formed and not chromones (*cf.* Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 536).

Incidentally, it may also be noted that 4-chloro-1-naphthol condenses with malic acid with as much ease as α -naphthol to yield 6-chloro-1:2- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone (I, R = R' = H) which undergoes inversion to naphtha-*o*-coumaric acid (III) when heated with mercuric oxide in alkaline solution (*cf.* Sen and Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 247).

(III)

4-Bromo-1-naphthol (Reverdin and Kaufmann, *Ber.*, 1895, 28, 3049) behaves similarly to 4-chloro-1-naphthol with the only difference that the reactions are generally less smooth in the case of bromo-naphthol and considerable amounts of tarry matter are invariably produced, which render the isolation of the product more difficult.

Thus, the study of the condensation of the halogenated α -naphthols with the acetoacetic esters brings the following facts into prominence :

(1) Three factors namely (a) the nature of the phenol, (b) the nature of the condensing agent, and (c) the nature of the β -ketonic ester determine the course of the condensation of a phenol with a β -ketonic ester to form a coumarin or a chromone.

(2) The results are in full agreement with the generalisation made by Chakravarti (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 31) regarding the nature of the product to be obtained by Simonis' reaction.

(3) The 2-methyl group in the 1:4- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrones is always reactive and this is a distinctive test from the isomeric 4-methyl-1:2- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrones.

(4) The 1:4- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrones, described in literature (*cf.* Bhullar and Venkataraman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1165), have been prepared by Allan and Robinson's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 2192), but the condensation of 4-chloro-1-naphthol with β -ketonic esters has furnished a ready method for the synthesis of substituted 1:4- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrones.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of 4-Chloro-1-naphthol (*cf.* Kast, *loc. cit.*).—Sulphuryl chloride (55 g.), diluted with chloroform (25 c.c.), was added drop by drop from a dropping funnel to a hot solution of α -naphthol (60 g.) in chloroform (90 c.c.), when vigorous reaction set in with evolution of

sulphur dioxide and hydrogen chloride. After all the sulphuryl chloride had been added the solution was boiled for a few minutes on a water-bath and left overnight. The colourless needles, separating, were filtered and crystallised from chloroform, m.p. 120-21°, yield 20-25 g.

6-Chloro-1:2- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone.—A mixture of 4-chloro-1-naphthol (8 g.) and malic acid (7 g.) was heated carefully on wire-gauze with sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84, 20 c.c.) (*cf.* preparation of umbelliferone, Dey, Rao and Seshadri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 746). The mixture began to froth in a few minutes and heating was continued until the liquid became clear. After cooling the mixture was poured into ice, the solid collected, washed with 2*N*-caustic soda and crystallised from dilute acetic acid as colourless needles, m.p. 163°. (Found: Cl,* 15.50. $C_{13}H_7O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 15.40 per cent).

7-Chloro- α -naphtha-o-coumaric Acid.—A solution of 6-chloro-1:2- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone (2 g.) in caustic potash solution (30 c.c., 16%) was diluted to 600 c.c. and boiled for 1 hour with powdered yellow mercuric oxide (2.5 g.). The solution was filtered and acidified with hydrochloric acid and the yellow precipitate dissolved in ammonia and the solution again acidified. The substance was crystallised from dilute alcohol as fine yellow needles, m.p. 185° (decomp.). The ammoniacal solution has a deep green fluorescence. (Found: Cl, 14.37. $C_{13}H_5O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 14.29 per cent).

6-Chloro-4-methyl-1:2- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone.—To a mixture of 4-chloro-1-naphthol (4 g.) and acetoacetic ester (4 c.c.), cooled in ice, sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84, 8 c.c.) was slowly added with constant shaking. The solution was kept overnight and poured on to ice, when a greenish solid separated. This was collected, treated with 2*N*-caustic soda, filtered and washed with water. It crystallised from glacial acetic acid (charcoal) as colourless needles, m.p. 219°, yield 5 g. (Found: Cl, 14.87. $C_{14}H_9O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 14.52 per cent).

The same compound was also obtained by using phosphorus pentoxide, sodium ethoxide and sodium acetate as condensing agents. No condensation was effected with phosphoric acid.

* The chlorine in the compounds, described in this paper, has been estimated by the semi-micro method (ter Meulen, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1928, 47, 698).

6-Chloro-3:4-dimethyl-1:2- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone, obtained from 4-chloro-1-naphthol (4 g.) and methyl-acetoacetic ester (4 g.) using sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84, 8 c. c.) in the usual manner, crystallised from glacial acetic acid as colourless needles, m. p. 203.4°, yield 2.8 g. (Found : Cl, 14.08. $C_{15}H_{11}O_2$ Cl requires Cl, 13.73 per cent). No condensation product could be isolated by condensing 4-chloro-1-naphthol with methyl-acetoacetic ester using sodium ethoxide as condensing agent; with sodium acetate as condensing agent an insoluble amorphous product was isolated which could not be crystallised.

6-Chloro-2:3-dimethyl-1:4- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone.—A mixture of 4-chloro-1-naphthol (5 g.), methyl-acetoacetic ester (5 c. c.) and phosphorus pentoxide (20 g.) was heated on the water-bath for 1 hour. The highly coloured mass was treated with water and the thick semi-solid product was washed with 2*N*-caustic soda solution, when a solid mixed with tarry matter was obtained. It crystallised from dilute acetic acid as pale yellow needles, m. p. 181.83°. (Found : Cl, 13.49. $C_{15}H_{11}O_2$ Cl requires Cl, 13.73 per cent). The solid, obtained by diluting the mother-liquor, was repeatedly crystallised from rectified spirit but no other product could be isolated.

6-Chloro-3-methyl-2-styryl-1:4- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone.—A solution of the above 1:4-naphthapyrone in alcohol was heated on the water-bath with alcoholic solution of sodium ethoxide and benzaldehyde. The solution on being diluted by a few drops of water deposited a yellow substance, which crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m. p. 188.90°. (Found : Cl, 10.48. $C_{22}H_{15}O_2$ Cl requires Cl, 10.24 per cent).

The other 1:2- and 1:4-naphthapyrones, prepared from 4-chloro-1-naphthol, are described in Table I.

1:2- and 1:4-Naphthapyrones from 4-Bromo-1-naphthol.—4-Bromo-1-naphthol was condensed with acetoacetic ester and α -alkylacetoacetic esters in presence of sulphuric acid or phosphorus pentoxide as condensing agents as in the case of 4-chloro-1-naphthol and the products obtained are described in Table II.

TABLE I.
Naphthalopyrones from 4-Chloro-1-naphthol.

Name.	Formula.	Prepared from.	Condensing agent.	M. P.	Analysis. Found.	Req.	Remarks.
6-Chloro-4-methyl-3-ethyl-1:2- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthopyrone	$C_{16}H_{19}O_2Cl$	Ethyl-acetoacetic ester and 4-chloro-1-naphthol	H_2SO_4	129-30°	Cl, 13.30%	13.02%	Crystallised from dilute alcohol as light yellow needles.
6-Chloro-2-methyl-3-ethyl-1:4- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthopyrone (I)	$C_{16}H_{19}O_2Cl$	"	P_2O_5	167-68°	13.26	13.02	Light yellow needles from rectified spirit.
6-Chloro-2-styryl-3-ethyl-1:4- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthopyrone	$C_{23}H_{17}O_2Cl$	(I) and benzaldehyde	NaOEt	194-95°	10.07	9.85	Crystallised from glacial acetic acid.
6-Chloro-4-methyl-3-propyl-1:2- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthopyrone	$C_{17}H_{19}O_2Cl$	Propyl-acetoacetic ester and 4-chloro-1-naphthol	H_2SO_4	104-5°	12.23	12.39	Crystallised from rectified spirit.
6-Chloro-2-methyl-3-propyl-1:4- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthopyrone (II)	$C_{17}H_{19}O_2Cl$	"	P_2O_5	126-27°	12.60	12.39	Colourless shining needles from rectified spirit
6-Chloro-2-styryl-3-propyl-1:4- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthopyrone.	$C_{24}H_{19}O_2Cl$	(II) and benzaldehyde	NaOEt	228°	9.63	9.48	Light yellow needles from glacial acetic acid
6-Chloro-4-methyl-3-isobutyl-1:2- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthopyrone	$C_{17}H_{17}O_2Cl$	Isobutyl-acetoacetic ester and 4-chloro-1-naphthol	H_2SO_4	136-38°	12.04	11.81	Crystallised from rectified spirit

TABLE I (contd.).

Name.	Formula.	Prepared from.	Condens- ing agent.	M. P.	Analysis.		Remarks.
					Found.	Req.	
6-Chloro-2-methyl-3-isobutyl-1:4- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone (III)	$C_{18}H_{17}O_4Cl$	Isobutyl-acetoacetic ester and 4-chloro-1-naphthol	P_2O_5	120-22°	Cl, 11.62%	11.81%	Crystallised from dilute alcohol.
6-Chloro-2-styryl-3-isobutyl-1:4- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone	$C_{18}H_{15}O_4Cl$	(III) and benzaldehyde	NaOHt	235-36°	9.40	9.14	Pale yellow needles from glacial acetic acid.
6-Chloro-4-methyl-3-benzyl-1:2- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone	$C_{20}H_{15}O_4Cl$	Benzyl-acetoacetic ester and 4-chloro-1-naphthol	H_2SO_4	200°	11.09	10.61	Colourless needles from glacial acetic acid. No product could be isolated using P_2O_5 .
3:6-Dichloro-4-methyl-1:2- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone	$C_{17}H_{13}O_4Cl_2$	α -Chloro-acetoacetic ester and 4-chloro-1-naphthol	H_2SO_4 or P_2O_5	257°	25.51	25.45	Crystallised from pyridine.
6-Chloro-4-phenyl-1:2- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone	$C_{19}H_{15}O_4Cl$	Benzoyl acetic ester and 4-chloro-1-naphthol	H_2SO_4	164°	11.34	11.58	Crystallised from dilute alcohol.
6-Chloro-4-methyl-3-phenyl-1:2- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone	$C_{20}H_{15}O_4Cl$	Phenyl-acetoacetic ester and 4-chloro-1-naphthol	H_2SO_4	215-16°	11.35	11.08	Pale yellow needles from glacial acetic acid.
6-Chloro-4-methyl-1:2- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone-3-acetic ester	$C_{19}H_{15}O_5Cl$	Acetosuccinic ester and 4-chloro-1-naphthol	H_2SO_4	181-84°	10.70	10.75	Colourless needles from absolute alcohol.
6-Chloro-1:2- $\alpha\beta$ -naphthapyrone-4-acetic acid	$C_{17}H_{13}O_5Cl$	Acetone dicarboxylic acid and 4-chloro-1-naphthol	H_2SO_4	212° (decomp.)	12.50	12.30	Crystallised from glacial acetic acid.

TABLE II
Naphthaphyrones from 4-Bromo-1-naphthol.

Name.	Formula.	Prepared from.	Condens- ing agent.	M. p.	Analysis.		Remarks.
					Found.	Req.	
6-Bromo-4-methyl- 1:2- $\alpha\beta$ -naphtha- pyrone.	$C_{11}H_9O_2Br$	Acetoacetic ester and 4-bromo-1-naph- thol	H_2SO_4 or P_2O_5	208°	Br, 27.24%	27.68%	Light yellow needles from glacial acetic acid.
6-Bromo-3:4-dimethyl- 1:2- $\alpha\beta$ -naphtha- pyrone	$C_{13}H_{11}O_2Br$	Methyl-acetoacetic ester and 4-bromo- 1-naphthol	H_2SO_4	187-89°	25.72	26.40	Crystallised from pyridine.
6-Bromo-2:3-dimethyl- 1:4- $\alpha\beta$ -naphtha- pyrone (I)	$C_{10}H_9O_2Br$	"	P_2O_5	211-12°	26.29	26.40	Colourless needles from dilute acetic acid.
6-Bromo-2-styryl-3-me- thyl-1:4- $\alpha\beta$ -naphtha- pyrone	$C_{20}H_{15}O_2Br$	(I) and benzaldehyde	NaOEt	233°	20.53	20.46	Crystallised from gla- cial acetic acid.
6-Bromo-4-methyl-3-beu- zyl-1:2- $\alpha\beta$ -naphtha- pyrone.	$C_{21}H_{19}O_2Br$	Benzyl-acetoacetic ester and 4-bromo- 1-naphthol	H_2SO_4	175-76°	20.59	21.11	Light yellow needles from pyridine. No product could be isolated using P_2O_5 .

The authors' best thanks are due to Prof. P. C. Mitter for giving them facilities to carry on this investigation.

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Received September 21, 1936